

Comparative Phytotoxicity Assessment of Treated and Untreated Tannery Effluent Using *Allium Cepa* L. (Onion Bulbs)¹

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Abstract

This study was conducted to assess the status of water quality through water monitoring and a comparative assessment of phytotoxicity. The study focused on how tannery effluent, which is chromium-based, is subjected to a single pollutant. A tannery effluent sample was collected from Kanpur. Physicochemical analysis was performed for different parameters. Heavy metals were identified by the AAS method. Organic and Inorganic compounds were detected by GC/MS analysis. Phytotoxicity was evaluated on different model plants. Seed germination test conducted on root growth inhibition on *Allium cepa*. Untreated tannery effluent is recognised as highly toxic in nature, as confirmed by phytotoxicity assay. Plant systems contribute to their increasing application in environmental monitoring. The *A. cepa*, is characterised as a low-cost test. It is easily handled and has advantages over other short tests. The present study revealed that the concentrations of pollutants present in tannery effluent are higher than the prescribed IS: 2490 limits and CPCB, 2012 limits. Therefore, the results of the present study suggest the wastewater quality, which deteriorated in the terms of chromium pollution which leads to phytotoxicity on different plant models.

Keywords

Heavy metals, GC-MS, Physicochemical parameters, Water pollution

INTRODUCTION

With the development of the tannery industry, tannery effluent has become one of the major sources of industrial pollution. The tannery industry is one of the oldest industries, which is unevenly scattered and more than 2,500 tanneries are located in different urban centres of India, processing about 500,000 tons of hides and skins per annum, which generate about 100,000 m³ of wastewater per day (Raj et al., 2014). This represents a high environmental and ecological risk in several

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countries, such as South Asia, which includes India and Pakistan, because of the highest number of tanning industries. Kanpur city is one of India's fastest-growing metropolitan cities. The city is spread over an area of about 1,640 km². In Jajmau, Kanpur (India), there are 203 tannery industries (Regional Office U.P. Pollution Control Board, Kanpur Nagar), and there are about 400 tanneries in Kanpur in all. In the tanning process, the use of chromium in several activities and consequent contamination of water have become increasing concerns. Tanneries are significant in terms of Indian exports and employment for people of economically opportunities for people of economical weaker populations. From the standpoint of economic growth, the Indian leather industry accounts for around 12.93 percent of the world's leather production of hides/skins. The country ranks second in terms of footwear and leather garments production and in the top 5, producing nearly 1.4 billion square feet of leather per year across the world (Raj et al., 2014). Tannery wastewater is ranked as the highest pollutants among all industries wastes. Tanneries generate wastewater in the range of 30-35 liters per kilogram of skin or hide processed with variable pH and high concentrations of pollutants (Durai G et al., 2011). Tanning is the process of treating skins and hides of animals to produce leather. A tannery is the place where the skins are processed. Tanning hide into leather involves a process which permanently alters the protein structure of skin, making it more durable and less susceptible to decomposition, and also possibly colouring it. However, sustenance of tanneries, particularly of the small units, is becoming increasingly difficult because of alarming levels of environmental pollution caused by various tanning operations and practices, and these small units can't afford their own wastewater treatment plant. Considering the financial and technological limitations of small units, the general approach adopted in India for the treatment of tannery wastewater from such units has been the commissioning of common effluent treatment plants (CETP) for tannery clusters. The tannery industry mushrooming in North India has converted the Ganga into a dumping ground. In the Kanpur belt, a large number of leather units are located at Jajmau area, right on the bank of the river Ganga. These units, which use many toxic chemicals, are the single largest contributor to the pollution of the surface as well as groundwater of the Jajmau area in Kanpur. Chromium in tanneries is capable of producing a deleterious response in a biological system, so it may be considered a poison in a biological system.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Sample Collection

Tannery effluent samples were collected from a leather-processing unit. Untreated effluent was obtained directly from the production line, while treated samples were collected after UASB-based biological treatment.

Physicochemical Analysis

Standard methods (APHA, 2017) were used to measure parameters including pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved solids (TDS), biological oxygen demand (BOD), chemical oxygen demand (COD), total hardness, sulfate, and chromium concentration.

Phytotoxicity Assay

Healthy onion bulbs (*Allium cepa* L.) were exposed to 0%, 25%, 50%, 75%, and 100% concentrations of treated and untreated effluent for 72 hours. Root length, mitotic index, and chromosomal aberrations were recorded according to the method of Fiskesjö (1985). Data were statistically analyzed using mean and standard deviation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table:1 the measured physicochemical parameters of the effluent samples and standards for tolerance limits of industrial wastewaters discharge into inland surface waters are given

S.NO.	Parameters	Untreated	Treated	Permissible limits
1.	Hexavalent chromium (Cr ₆ ⁺) (mg/l)	0.85	0.63	0.1
2.	BOD ₅ (mg/l)	1500.0	180.0	30
3.	DO	Nil	Nil	-
4.	pH	8.93	8.37	6.0-9.0
5.	Ammonical nitrogen (mg/l)	234.08	153.44	50
6.	Phosphate (mg/l)	10.3	15.8	5.0
7.	COD (mg/l)	3434.0	442.0.0	250
8.	Sulphate (mg/l)	2591.0	422.2	1000
9.	Sulphide (mg/l)	0.33	0.36	2.0
10.	TKN (mg/l)	244.16	170.24	100
11.	Nitrate (mg/l)	132.23	174.45	10
12.	Nitrite (mg/l)	3.14	2.23	-
13.	TS(mg/l)	22870.0	4962.0	-
14.	TDS(mg/l)	13430.0	4422.0	2100
15.	TSS(mg/l)	9440.0	540.0	100
16.	FS(mg/l)	12684.0	4432.0	-
17.	VFS(mg/l)	10186.0	530.0	-
18.	Chloride(mg/l)	5848.2	2249.3	1000
19.	Fluoride (mg/l)	0.58	0.31	2.0
20.	Oil and Grease(mg/l)	1425.5	4320.0	10

Table:2 the measured heavy metal analysis of the effluent samples and standards for tolerance limits of industrial wastewaters discharge into inland surface waters are given.

S.No.	Parameters	Untreated (mg/l)	Treated (mg/l)	Permissible Limits
1.	Total chromium (Cr)	8.4	5.0	2.0
2.	Cobalt (Co)	0.2	0.1	-
3.	Iron (Fe)	0.5	0.6	3.0
4.	Copper (Cu)	0.0	0.0	3.0
5.	Manganese (Mn)	0.1	0.1	2
6.	Lead (Pb)	0.2	0.1	0.1
7.	Zinc (Zn)	0.1	0.1	5.0
8.	Nickel (Ni)	0.2	0.1	3.0

Analysis of organic pollutants of tannery effluent by using Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectroscopy (GC/MS) results

Figure:1 typical chromatographic profile obtained by GC-MS of compounds extracted with dichloromethane from untreated tannery effluent sample. MS-identified compounds with respect to their retention times are listed in Table: 4.3

Figure:2 typical chromatographic profile obtained by GC-MS of compounds extracted with dichloromethane from treated tannery effluent sample. MS-identified compounds with respect to their retention times are listed in Table:4.4

Figure:3 typical chromatographic profile obtained by GC-MS of compounds extracted with ethyl acetate from untreated tannery effluent sample. MS-identified compounds with respect to their retention times are listed in Table: 4.5

Figure:4 typical chromatographic profile obtained by GC-MS of compounds extracted with ethyl acetate from treated tannery effluent sample. MS-identified compounds with respect to their retention times are listed in Table: 4.6

Table: 4 Compounds identified in dichloromethane extract from untreated tannery effluent sample as given in Figure: 4.1

S.No.	RT (in min,)	COMPOUND NAME (as per NIST library)	MAJOR FRAGMENTS
1	7.45	D-LACTIC ACID-DITMS	147, 117, 73
2.	8.77	E-2-(4'-Tolyl)-1-(phenylsulfonyl)ethane	258
3.	13.47	p-tert-Butylphenyldisulphide	330, 315
4.	15.39	METHYL 13C HEXADECADIENOATE	254, 211, 120, 73
5.	17.36	Acetic-acid, bis[(trimethylsilyl)oxyl]-, trimethylsilyl ester (CAS)	191, 147, 73
6.	19.75	Pentanoic acid,5-[bis(trimethylsilyl)amino]-, trimethylsilyl ester	318, 174, 73
7.	21.09	D-erythro-Pentonic acid, 3-deoxy-2,5-bis-O-(trimethylsilyl)-2-C-[[[(trimethylsilyl)oxy]methyl]-, ζ -lactone (CAS)	348 , 245, 147, 117,103
8.	23.33	Cinnamic acid, m-methoxy-, trimethylsilyl ester (CAS)	293 ,235, 147, 73
9.	26.08	5,8,11-Heptadecatriynoic acid, methyl ester	115, 141, 129, 115, 91, 55, 41
10.	29.98	Octadecanoic acid, trimethylsilyl ester	341, 145, 132, 117, 75, 43
11.	33.23	3-Benzoyl-2,5-diphenyl-4-(1,1-dimethyl-6-indanoyl)thiophene	514, 513, 512
12.	36.79	Octadecane, 1,1'-[1,3-propanediylbis(oxy)]bis-	310, 281, 71, 57

Table: 4 Compounds identified in dichloromethane extract from treated tannery effluent sample as given in Figure: 4.2

S. No.	RT (In min)	COMPOUND NAME (as per NIST library)	MAJOR FRAGMENTS
1.	7.85	N-Methyl-N-(2,4,6- trimethylphenyl)formamide	177, 147
2.	8.76	E-2-(4'-Tolyl)-1-(phenylsulfonyl)ethane	258
3.	12.42	Trimethylsilyl ether of glycerol	205, 147, 117, 103, 73
4.	13.67	Propanoic acid, 2,3- bis[(trimethylsilyl)oxy]-, trimethylsilyl ester	292, 189, 147, 73
5.	15.40	Benzo[b]naphtho[1,2-d]thiophene (CAS)	234, 232
6.	17.35	1,1,1-Tris(hydroxymethyl)propane, tris(trimethylsilyl) ether	191, 151, 147, 73
7.	21.09	D-threo-Pentonic acid, 3-deoxy-2,5-bis-O- (trimethylsilyl)-2-C-[[[(trimethylsilyl)oxy]methyl]-, lactone	348, 147, 117, 103
8.	22.92	Bis(trimethylsilyl)-2-Methyl-2,4- bis(trimethylsilyl oxy)glutarate	259, 147, 3
9.	27.03	1-Methoxy-3-pentyl-6,6a,7,8-tetrahydro- 6,6-dime thyl- 9H-dibenzo[b,d]pyran-9-one	328, 313
10.	29.97	Octadecanoic acid, trimethylsilyl ester	341, 132, 117, 73
11.	33.22	Docosane (CAS)	85, 71, 57, 43
12.	36.79	QUERCETIN 7,3',4'-TRIMETHOXY	73, 57, 53
13.	47.66	26,28-Dihydroxy-25,27-dioxaocta-4-ene- 2,6-diynyl-p- tert-butylcalix[4]arene	No fragments

Table:5 Compounds identified in ethyl acetate extract from untreated tannery effluent sample as given in Figure 3

S.No.	RT (in min,)	COMPOUND NAME (as per NIST library)	MAJOR FRAGMENTS
1.	6.69	2-DEUTERO-2-ETHYLMALONATE 2TMS	147, 73, 56
2.	8.76	E-2-(4'-Tolyl)-1-(phenylsulfonyl)ethane	258
3.	12.60	9-Octadecen-12-ynoic acid, methyl ester	71, 57
4.	15.81	Benzeneacetic acid, à-[(trimethylsilyl)oxy]-, trimethylsilyl ester (CAS)	179, 147, 73
5.	17.12	Docosane (CAS)	85, 71, 57, 43
6.	21.17	Docosane (CAS)	85, 71, 57, 43

7.	24.82	Docosane, 11-decyl- (CAS)	85, 71, 57, 43
8.	26.11	1,8,15,22-Tricosatetrayne	171, 91, 79
9.	28.14	Docosane (CAS)	85, 71, 57, 43
10.	31.02	Docosane (CAS)	85, 71, 57, 43
11.	33.21	Nonacosane (CAS)	85, 71, 57, 43
12.	35.08	7-(Trimethylsilyloxy)-3-[4-(trimethylsilyloxy)phenyl]-4H-1 benzopyran-4-one	399, 398, 383
13.	36.79	9,12,15-Octadecatrienoic acid, 2,3- bis[(trimethylsilyl)oxy]propyl ester, (Z,Z,Z)	149, 75
14.	38.89	Ethyl 3,4-Dimethoxybenzoacetate	488, 459, 458
15.	47.65	5,11,17-23-tetrakis(1,1-dimethylethyl)-28- methoxypentacyclo[19.3.1.1(3,7).1(9,13).1(15,19)]octacosa- 1(25),3,5,7(28),9,11,13(27),15,17,19(26),21,23-dode cene-25,26,27-triol	663, 662, 647

Table:6 Compounds identified in Ethyl acetate from treated tannery effluent sample as given in Figure: 4

S.No.	RT (in min,)	COMPOUND NAME (as per NIST library)	MAJOR FRAGMENTS
1.	7.46	9-Methylenetricyclo[4.3.0.0(3,8)]non-4-enyl)tosyl hydrazone	91, 57
2.	8.75	E-2-(4'-Tolyl)-1-(phenylsulfonyl)ethane	258
3.	13.15	Benzeneacetic acid, trimethylsilyl ester	75, 73
4.	17.10	Docosane (CAS)	85, 71, 57, 43
5.	20.02	Benzeneacetic acid, 3-[(trimethylsilyl)oxy]-, trimethylsilyl ester	73
6.	21.16	Tritetracontane (CAS)	85, 71, 57, 43
7.	24.80	7,9-Di-tert-butyl-1-oxaspiro(4,5)deca-6,9-diene-2,8-dione	205, 57, 41
8.	27.01	Hexadecanoic acid, trimethylsilyl ester	313, 117, 75, 73
9.	29.96	Octadecanoic acid, trimethylsilyl ester	117, 75, 73, 43
10.	33.22	Nonacosane (CAS)	85, 71, 57, 43
11.	35.47	QUERCETIN 7,3',4'-TRIMETHOXY	73, 57, 55
12.	47.65	4-HYDROXY-3-(2-OXO-2H-1-OXA-3-PHENANTHRYL)- 2(1H)-QUINOLINONE	649, 648

Allium cepa

The results of the effect of the effluent on root growth of *A. cepa* shown in Table 7. The phytotoxicity assay was done with four different concentrations of the effluent sample, with a control. Besides the

control, the highest growth was recorded at 0% concentration and the least concentration at 25% concentration.

Figure:5 the figure represents the root length of *A. cepa* after treatment with different concentrations of tannery effluent.

Table:7 Inhibition of root length of *A. cepa* following treatment with different concentrations of tannery effluent.

Sample	Concentration (%)	Root length (cm)
Untreated	0	8.6 ± 0.4
	6.25	2.9 ± 0.1
	12.5	2.7 ± 0.1
	25	1.6 ± 0.1
Treated	0	9.8 ± 0.5
	6.25	3.4 ± 0.2
	12.5	3.2 ± 0.2
	25	2.9 ± 0.1

Values are mean ± SD of three samples.

DISCUSSION

Analysis of Physicochemical parameters and comparison in terms of treated water quality and quantity of tannery effluent

The measured physicochemical parameters of the effluent samples and standards for tolerance limits of industrial wastewaters discharge into inland surface waters are given in Table: 4.1. The effluent pH was measured to be 8.93 in untreated and 8.37 in treated which are alkaline. It was within the tolerance limits, inland surface waters. The values of anions present in wastewater namely, NO_3^- , Cl^- , PO_4^{3-} were found to be above the permissible limits prescribed by CPCB (MOEF&CC), therefore the result showed that treatment is not suitable for removing ions from wastewater. Usually, the incorporation in biological systems prevents the removal of phosphorous by the addition of flocculants

and also by the operation of solid separation. The average values of BOD and COD were found to be significantly higher than the prescribed IS: 2490 (part-1)1981 and CPCB, 2012. BOD which indicates the pollution strength of the waste waters was recorded as 1500 mg/l and 750 mg/l in untreated and treated effluent mg/L respectively. High BOD is harmful to aquatic animals like fish and microorganisms. The COD value of the effluent samples was recorded as 3434 mg/l and 442 mg/l in untreated and treated effluent respectively. High COD levels indicate the toxic state of the waste water along with the presence of biologically resistant organic substances. Further, effluents were found to be containing high level of solids. TDS (13430 and 4422 mg/l), TSS (9440 and 7983 mg/l), TS (22870 and 4962 mg/l) was recorded in untreated and treated effluent. The sulfate ions present in effluent was recorded as 2591 and 422.2 mg/l in untreated and treated effluent and found to be higher concentration in untreated effluent prescribed by IS: 2490 (part-1),1981. The concentrations of sulfides in tannery affluent was found to be in the range of 0.33 mg/l and 0.36 mg/l in untreated and treated effluent, within the prescribed limit (CPCB, MoEF&CC). The forms of nitrogen namely, total kjeldahl nitrogen (244.16 mg/l and 170.24 mg/l) and Ammonical nitrogen (234.08 mg/l and 153.44 mg/l) in untreated and treated effluent were found to be higher than the prescribed limits (CPCB, MoEF&CC). The nitrogen forms cause: algal blooms, eutrophication, and toxicity to fish and other organisms, health disorders. Ammonical nitrogen and organic nitrogen which are essential nutrients for growth but higher concentration cause toxicity. The hexavalent chromium was found to be significantly higher than the prescribed limits (CPCB, MoEF), 0.55 mg/l and 0.65 mg/l in untreated and treated

Analysis of inorganic pollutants of tannery effluent by using AAS

The measured heavy metal analysis of the effluent samples and standards for tolerance limits of industrial wastewaters discharge into inland surface waters are given in Table:

4.2. The data show that in the effluent samples, the trace elements total chromium (Cr) and lead (Pb) were among the dominant metals. Cr was recorded as 8.4 and 5.0 mg/l in untreated and treated effluent which exceeds the prescribed limits (CPCB, MoEF&CC). Pb was found to be 0.2 and 0.1 mg/l in untreated and treated effluent. In the effluent samples

Fe, Cu, Mn, Zn and Ni have low values and Cu is in the lowest position, having zero concentration in both untreated and treated effluent, respectively. The order of the metals' abundance in tannery based on metal analysis values is Cr > Pb > Fe > Ni > Zn > Mn > Cu. It shows that the data shows positive results in metals Fe, Cu, Mn, Zn, Ni and negative and highly toxic results in metals Cr and Pb.

Analysis of organic pollutants of tannery effluent by using Gas Chromatography/Mass Spectroscopy (GC-MS):

GC/MS for nonpolar organics allows one to identify many chemicals in a mixture. Typical chromatographic profile obtained by GC-MS of compounds extracted with DCM and ethyl acetate solvents from untreated and treated tannery effluent samples. MS- identified compounds with respect to their retention times are listed in Table3,4, and 5,4.6 and figures: 4.1, 4.2, 4.3, and 4.4.

There are so many constituents within the class of chemicals identified in GC/MS. The compounds were detected by GC-MS in DCM extracts of untreated and treated effluent are shown in Figures 1, 2 and Tables 3, 4. The effluent was recorded in untreated effluent with Pentanoic acid (RT=19.75) and (RT=21.09), Phenyl compounds (RT=13.47), Lactic acids (RT=7.45), Acetic acid (17.36), Cinnamic acid (23.33), Octadecanoic acid (29.98). The effluent was recorded in the treated sample with Trimethylsilyl (RT=12.42, 13.67), Docosane (RT=33.22).

The compounds were detected by GCMS in ethyl acetate extracts of untreated and treated effluent are shown in Figure 4.3, 4.4 and Table 4.5, 4.6. The compounds was recorded in untreated effluent with Docosane (RT=17.12, 21.17, 28.14, 31.02) and Benzeneacetic acid (RT=15.81). The compounds were recorded in treated effluent with Docosane (RT=17.10) and Tritetracontane (RT=21.10). GC-MS analysis indicates that treated effluent still contains various persistent organic pollutants even after secondary biological treatment. GC/MS considered as powerful tool to identify the organic compounds in wastewater.

Allium cepa:

The result of the root inhibition test conducted using *A. cepa*, L. ($2n = 16$) is summarised in Table 4.7, and the morphological observation is shown in Figure 5. The onion bulbs were exposed in control (dechlorinated tap water) show luxuriant root growth measured 9.8 and 8.6 cm. On the other hand, onion bulbs exposed to different concentrations of untreated and treated tannery effluent exhibit a reduction in root growth and length. The reduction was concentration dependent manner and the maximum reduction was observed with untreated tannery effluent (25%), which caused 81% reduction in root length. When compared to the control. Similarly, of 25% treated tannery effluent caused 70% inhibition in root length of *A. cepa* when compared to the control.

The result clearly indicates the phytotoxic effects of both untreated and treated tannery effluent. The inhibition in root length of *A. cepa* due to the exposure to tannery effluent may be correlated to the cytotoxic effect of pollutants present in the effluent.

Conclusion

Tannery effluents were collected from the Jajmau-Kanpur plant, and physiochemical analyses of tannery effluents were carried out in this study. Tannery effluent was found to be higher in BOD, COD, TDS, TSS, TS, NO_3^- , Cl^- , PO_4^{3-} anion concentration as compared to the limits prescribed by the IS: 2490 Part-1 (1981). Hexavalent chromium and total chromium were found to be higher than prescribed limits and since it is a pollution indicator which is highly toxic to environment therefore, physiochemical release from tannery is the major source of water pollution in the Kanpur. GC-MS analysis showed the toxic compounds were present in untreated effluent but after treatment there was reduction in toxic compounds were observed. In this study tannery effluent have been used to illustrate the potential of plant system as monitors. After conducting experimentations it has been found effluents is highly toxic as it has been confirmed by conducting phytotoxicity assay on plant model organism using *Allium cepa*, Fenugreek, and *Brassica campestris*. These plant systems appear

to be excellent indicators of the phytotoxicity and phytotoxic effects leading to cellular and functional changes to cell death. Therefore it is recommended that plant systems be accepted as assay system for the detection of possible damage resulting from the use of environmental chemicals in this study. The tannery effluent discharged into natural environment will disturb the ecosystem and therefore there is a need for proper treatment of pollutants. The amounts of pollutants introduced into the environment through tanneries puts undoubtedly endanger the ecological balance if the wastewaters from different sources are not treated prior to disposal or reuse. Indeed, negative impacts are observed on plant system. A first observation can be made through the obtained results (average values found in TSS, BOD₅ and COD) the presence of a strong and irregular organic pollution from tannery effluent from the Jajmau (Kanpur) could be dangerous to the receiving environment. It is necessary to use further analysis by other techniques to refine this characterization and to improve the identification of the possible contamination sources.

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